

Vibration measurements of the SC72 gradient versus field strength in the Iseult magnet

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Synopsis: The whole-body Iseult 11.7T CEA magnet has delivered its first images after nearly 20 years of research and development. Before reaching this long-awaited step, a gradient coil–magnet interaction test campaign was run for several months at 3T, 7T, 10.2T and 11.7T on the same identical system. It included acoustics, vibrations, magnet safety system voltage and power deposition in the He bath measurements. Some vibration results versus field strength are presented here. Vibration amplitudes are shown to increase less than with B_0 field strength.

Purpose: MRI at UHF offers great promises in SNR and CNR. In the quest of reaching ever higher magnetic fields, one crucial aspect beforehand remains the design of the magnet, the gradient coil and their interaction. The time-varying fields generated by the gradient cause eddy-currents in the structure which, under the influence of a strong B_0 field, generate vibrations, which engender themselves electric fields and power deposition in the He bath. In addition to these power losses which can be critical for the integrity of the magnet, mechanical resonances also can be detrimental for imaging performance (e.g. ghosting). In this context, we report in this work vibration measurements on the SC72 (Siemens Healthineers, Erlangen, Germany) whole-body gradient in the bore of the Iseult magnet at 3T, 7T, 10.2T and 11.7T.

Methods: The Iseult magnet¹ is 5 m long/wide and weighs 132 tons. The main superconducting coil is immersed into a He bath of 7000 liters cooled down to 1.8 K, where He is superfluid. The gradient coil is surrounded by a lead tube to screen gradient-magnet interactions at some frequencies². Six mono-axial accelerometers (Hottinger Bruel & Kjaer, Naerum, Denmark) were glued on the gradient, the lead tube and the cryostat to measure accelerations along the X and Y directions (Fig. 1). Vibrations were measured by applying a 1-min chirp excitation on the 3 gradient axis separately with $G=1$ mT/m over the 0-3200 Hz range. Close to a well-defined natural frequency ω_0 , the response of the accelerometers on the gradient was temptingly modeled with a damped harmonic oscillator: $\ddot{u} + \eta\dot{u} + \omega_0^2 u = F(t)/m$, where m is an effective mass and where the damping coefficient η shall vary with B_0 . Because of the Lorentz force, the force should be proportional to the current and the static field, i.e. $F \propto IB_0$. For an oscillating force at angular frequency ω , assuming a large quality factor, solving the differential equation in the steady state yields approximately for the peak displacement $u_{max} \propto IB_0/\eta$. To verify this simple model, measurements were performed at 0.1, 1 and 5 mT/m to confirm the linearity of the response versus I , for B_0 constant. They were finally repeated on the same identical system at 3T, 7T, 10.2T and 11.7T to study the response and the dependence of η on B_0 over a broad frequency range.

Results: Fig.2.a. shows the measured temporal displacement along the Y axis for a sine excitation of $G_Y=20$ mT/m at 550 Hz and at 7T, with its Fourier transform. Fig.2.b shows acceleration spectra acquired at 11.7T for the three gradient axis and normalized by the different gradient strengths. The plots being nearly identical and the system responding at the frequency of the excitation indicate a behavior consistent with a harmonic oscillator. Fig. 3 shows the acceleration spectra under a $G=1$ mT/m excitation at different B_0 field strengths and for the three gradient axis, showing qualitatively the same behavior aside from expected increased amplitudes versus field strength. The amplitude of the peaks, normalized to the one at 3T, is shown in Fig. 4 and reveals a response that grows slower than the B_0 field.

Discussion and conclusion: To a good approximation, the experimental results show that the vibration response at one location of the gradient coil is consistent with a damped harmonic oscillator. The data reveal

a less severe dependence for the response than with B_0 , which may also explain the moderate increase of acoustic noise versus field strength³ for a same set up. Having $\eta \propto B_0$ would yield a nearly constant amplitude response versus B_0 , which is not the case. Interestingly, some resonances also exhibit a plateau which could be consistent with a dependence of the damping coefficient as $\eta(\omega) \propto \eta_0(\omega) + \alpha B_0$ (with α being a scalar). The data, at least up to 11.7T, on the other hand cannot verify a dependence as $\eta(\omega) \propto \eta_0(\omega) + \alpha B_0^2$ as suggested in the literature⁴ which would imply an increase of the response until a maximum is reached, followed by a drop versus field strength.

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Figure 1. Accelerators placement. The green, orange and blue arrows point towards the mono-axial accelerometers positioned on the gradient, the lead tube and the cryostat respectively.

Figure 2. Harmonic oscillator consistency check. a) Temporal displacement waveform measured on the gradient by one accelerometer ($G_Y=20$ mT/m at 550 Hz and at 7T) and its Fourier transform. The system responds at the same frequency as the excitation. Small harmonic components can remain due to a non-ideal excitation. b) Acceleration spectra acquired at 11.7T on the three different gradient axis and normalized by different gradient strength. Similar curves indicate linearity of the response versus gradient strength or current.

Figure 3. Acceleration spectra for $G=1$ mT/m at 3T, 7T, 10.2T and 11.7T and for the three different axis. The amplitude of the response increases while the spectra remain qualitatively the same.

Figure 4. Normalized peak displacements at different resonances for the three gradient axis. Results were normalized by the response at 3T for better readability of the peak behavior at different frequencies. The dashed line is the $(3T-11.7T)/3T$ normalized straight line. All resonance strengths evolve less quickly than B_0 . Some of them even reach a plateau, at least up to 11.7T.